

Studies in some N-Acyl N-Phenylhydroxylamines as Metal-Complexing Ligands. Part VI. N-Phenyl N-Hydroxysuccinamic Acid

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Complex compounds of Cu(II) and Ni(II) with N-phenyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid (RH₂) as ligand, are Cu(R)(H₂O)₂ and Ni(R)(H₂O)₂ isolated. Magnetic data, d-d spectra in mull and i.r. spectra in KBr matrix of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes, and electronic spectra of RH₂ and RHN_a in aqueous solution, and i.r. spectra of RH₂ in KBr matrix have been recorded. From the spectral study of Fe(III)-RH₂ system in aqueous solution, the formation of two different complexes of compositions (1 : 1) and (2 : 3) at pH-values 1.87 and 3.25 has been observed.

A NUMBER of N-acyl N-phenylhydroxylamines have already been studied in our laboratory¹⁻⁵. To study the properties of another series of such hydroxamic acids, the compound N-phenyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid which may also be stated as N-phenylhydroxylamine N-propionyl β-carboxylic acid (RH₂), has been synthesised. A preliminary note has been published⁶.

It forms complex compounds with Fe(III), Cu(II), Ni(II), V(V) and U(VI). Cu(II) and Ni(II) compounds are isolated in the solid state. A spectral study of Fe(III)-RH₂ system in aqueous solution has also been made and observed that absorption peaks are shifted towards lower wavelengths on raising pH of the solutions—indicating the formation of different complexes in solutions. Their compositions, by Job's method of continuous variation⁷ have been determined.

Experimental

A. Preparation of the ligand—N-phenyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid :

The compound was prepared by condensing succinic anhydride (1 mole) with excess of phenyl hydroxylamine (1.5 mole) in ice cold benzene solution containing 10% dry pyridine. The compound was crystallised from aqueous ethanol. It is a white crystalline solid—m.p. 113°, soluble in ethanol, acetone, ether, benzene and moderately so in water. Found : C, 57.10; H, 5.55; N, 6.58; C₁₀H₁₁O₄N requires C, 57.41; H, 5.26; N, 6.69%.

B. Complex Compound of Cu(II) :

To the aqueous solution of the ligand (1 mole) ammoniacal copper sulphate (1.2 mole) solution was

added. The resulting greenish solution after treatment with charcoal was treated with dil. H₂SO₄ drop by drop till pH ≈ 3, when bright green crystals of Cu(II) compound separated as Cu(R)(H₂O)₂. It was purified by dissolving in cold aqueous ammonia, treating with charcoal, filtering and treating the filtrate with dil. H₂SO₄ as usual. The crystals were washed thoroughly with water and finally with ethanol and air dried. Found : Cu, 20.60; N, 4.60; Cu(R)(H₂O)₂ requires Cu, 20.65; N, 4.55%. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, DMF etc. It decomposes slowly on heating at 105°.

C. Complex Compound of Ni(II) :

To ethanolic solution of the nickel acetate (1 mole), ethanolic solution of excess ligand was added with stirring, when a light green compound Ni(R)(H₂O)₂ separated. Filtered, washed thoroughly with ethanol and air dried. Found : Ni, 19.20; N, 4.50; Ni(R)(H₂O)₂ requires Ni, 19.47; N, 4.60%. The compound is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, DMF etc. On heating at 100° it decomposes slowly.

The magnetic moment values after correction for diamagnetism and d-d spectra in mull of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes and electronic spectra of RH₂ and RHN_a in aqueous solution were measured at room temperature and their data are stated in Table 1. The i.r. spectra of RH₂, Cu(R)(H₂O)₂ and Ni(R)(H₂O)₂ in KBr matrix have been studied and the probable assignments^{8,9} of some important vibrations are recorded in Table 2.

D. Complex Compounds of Fe(III) :

The ligand forms a brilliant red colour with Fe(III). The compositions of Fe(III) complexes were determined by Job's method of continuous variation.

All reagents used were A.R. quality. Optical densities were measured with a spectrophotometer (UVISPEK) using 1 cm quartz cell against water as blank. pH values were adjusted with a Cambridge pH meter (portable type).

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC DATA OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) COMPLEXES, ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF RH₂ AND RHNa IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION, AND THE DATA OF THE D-D SPECTRA IN MULL OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	μ_{eff} in B.M.	Temperature in °K	λ_{max}^{aq} in nm	log ϵ	λ_{max}^{mull} in nm	O.D. in arbitrary unit
Cu(R)(H ₂ O) ₂	1.89	302.5	—	—	650	0.614
Ni(R)(H ₂ O) ₂	3.14	304.0	—	—	640	0.394
RH ₂	—	—	209	3.80	—	—
			242	3.77		
RHNa	—	—	209	3.76	—	—
			245	3.73		

TABLE 2—I.R. SPECTRAL DATA OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) COMPLEXES AND LIGANDS

RH ₂	Frequencies cm ⁻¹		Assignment (Probable)
	Cu(R)(H ₂ O) ₂	Ni(R)(H ₂ O) ₂	
...	3334(sh.w.)	3334(b.st.)	H-bonded water molecule.
3200(sp.st.)	O-H stretching vibration.
1717(sp.st.)	due to -COOH.
...	1603(sh.st.)	1613(sh.st.)	COO ⁻ antisymmetrical stretching.
1646(sp.st.)	1575(sp.st.)	1575(b.st.)	C=O stretching.
...	1568(sh.st.)	1568(sh.st.)	due to lattice or coordinated water.
...	1398(sp.st.)	1408(sh.st.)	COO ⁻ symmetrical stretching.
...	1015(sp.m.)	1015(sp.m.)	due to co-ordinated water.
933(b.m.)	1002(sp.st.)	1000(sp.m.)	N-O stretching vibration.

sp = sharp; b = broad; sh = shoulder; st = strong; m = medium; w = weak.

In studying the compositions of the complexes of Fe(III) by Job's method, first spectral curves were drawn at different pH-values. 2 ml of 0.0045M ferric perchlorate solutions and 10 ml of 0.0027M ligand solution were taken in each of a number of 25 ml measuring flasks, requisite amount of sodium perchlorate was added to maintain ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) after adjusting to the desired pH-values, the volume were made upto the mark. Optical densities of these solutions were measured in the range 960 to 370 nm against water as blank. Data are presented graphically by plotting O.D. against corresponding wavelength (Fig. 1).

From the Curves, peaks 490 nm and 470 nm were chosen to study the composition by Job's method of continuous variation at pH \approx 1.87 and 3.25 respectively. In order to find out the composition, two different equimolecular solutions of Fe(III) and the ligand ($9 \times 10^{-4}M$ and $5 \times 10^{-4}M$) prepared separately, each containing 0.5M NaClO₄, were mixed together in different ratios in a number of 25 ml measuring flasks, after adjusting pH, the volumes were made upto the mark. The optical densities of these solutions were measured at the selected wavelengths

against water. Optical densities were plotted against composition of the solutions.

Fig. 1. Spectral curves for Fe(III) chelates I, pH - 1.87; II, pH - 2.3; III, pH - 2.75; IV, pH - 3.00; V, pH - 3.25.

Discussion

The ligand may act as a monoprotic or biprotic bidentate or a biprotic tridentate one. Cu(II) and Ni(II) compounds of the ligand are isolated in the solid state and both of them have (1 : 1) compositions. In these compounds the ligand appears to behave as a biprotic tridentate one supported by i.r. spectral data.

Magnetic moment of Cu(II) compound has been found to be 1.89 B.M. suggesting a high spin complex with square planar or distorted octahedral¹⁰ configuration. The Ni(II) complex has the magnetic moment 3.14 B.M.—the value expected for high spin octahedral¹¹ complex. The electronic spectra

of Cu(II) complex shows characteristics band in the region 900 to 600 nm¹¹. However, absorption maxima found at 650 nm of the mull spectra supports square planar or highly distorted octahedral structure. Regarding electronic spectra of Ni(II) complex, there are three allowed transitions for octahedral configuration. The d-d band found at 640 nm may be assigned to the transition $3A_{2g}$ to $3T_{1g}$ (F).

In aqueous solutions of the ligand RH_2 and its sodium salt $RHNa$, there are two characteristics bands around 209 and 242 nm which are assigned as benzene bands^{12,13}.

The O-H stretching vibrations are found in the region 3650–3500 cm^{-1} . The bands at 3200 cm^{-1} in the ligand (Table 2) shows the presence of strongly hydrogen-bonded OH group in the ligand. The strong bands 1646 cm^{-1} and 1717 cm^{-1} in the ligand are assigned due to C=O and COOH grouping respectively and that at 933 cm^{-1} due to N-O stretching vibration. In the Cu(II) and Ni(II) compounds, the disappearance of the band around 3200 cm^{-1} , suggesting the bonding N-O-M and the appearance of the new bands at 3334 cm^{-1} are obviously due to presence of hydrogen-bonded water molecules. Bands at 1568 cm^{-1} and 1015 cm^{-1} are due to presence of co-ordinated water molecule. Data in Table 2 show a shift of -COOH stretching vibration in the metal complexes; the symmetrical and antisymmetrical stretchings are also shown^{9,14}. Data suggest the

presence of $\begin{array}{c} O \\ // \\ -C \\ \backslash \\ O-M \end{array}$ type of bonding. Similar shift

of C=O stretching vibration towards lower frequencies and N-O stretching vibration towards higher frequencies in the Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes (Table 2) suggesting the bonding of these groups with the metal atom.

By Job's method of continuous vibration, the existence of two different complexes of Fe(III) and RH_2 has been indicated. The purple complex (1 : 1) at $\lambda = 490$ nm and $pH = 1.87$, the red complex (2 : 3) at $\lambda = 470$ nm and $pH = 3.25$ have been observed.

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